

Crisis-Induced Hospital Financial Performance and Quality of Care: Evidence From Portugal¹

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The recent economic crisis has had a profound impact on individual health and healthcare systems triggering variations in population health and income all around Europe. In Portugal its effect was aggravated by austerity measures taken in response to economic conditions leading to changes in hospital budgets and capacities. While the relationship between the crisis and healthcare utilization has been addressed in the literature, its impact on the quality of care remains an open empirical question. This study aims at investigating the impact of the crisis induced financial hardship on the evolution of the quality of hospital care in Portugal distinguishing between demand-side and supply-side effects.

Methods: The study conducts a comprehensive analysis of hospital care quality indicators currently in the EU. Next, the paper combines local municipality level data and hospital-level financial condition data with hospital-level DRG data for Portugal for the period 2013-2017 and uses the GMM approach to infer the demand and supply-side effects of the crisis-induced changes in hospital financial performance on the evolution of quality of hospital services provided. The analysis accounts for the severity of health outcomes across several domains of hospital care, namely DRGs with high and low mortality outcomes, thereby examining impact of the hospital financial performance in the aftermath of the economic crisis on a range of hospital care quality indicators derived from the DRG data, including mortality rates, hospital readmissions, patient safety related measures and other quality indicators identified in the literature.

Results: Preliminary results show that the economic crisis has not had a statistically significant impact on the quality of hospital care in Portugal. The results are in line with existing literature investigating the impact of economic crisis in Portugal and with studies conducted in the US setting for the same quality of care indicators.

Discussion: The findings of the study suggest that there is no effect, however they may be sensitive to model specification and quality indicators in use. Hence, further investigation is needed to understand the mechanisms behind the impact, especially in terms of use of alternative quality of care indicators.

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